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Impact Factor: 2.625

DOI : <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.293821>

Cite this paper as : C .M. JACOB & J .K. TANDON (2017), A STUDY ON FACADES OF THE TALL BUILDINGS IN UAE, International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research, ISSN: 2349 –3593 (online), ISSN: 2349 –4816 (print), Vol.4,(Issue17,Jan-2017), pp 72–pp ,82, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.293821>

A STUDY ON FACADES OF THE TALL BUILDINGS IN UAE

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Abstract

This is a research study on façades of tall buildings in United Arab Emirates as a part of detailed research on “a critical study of decision making process in the project management of facades for the tall buildings in UAE”. This study is relevant as UAE is the home land of Tallest building in the world. There are 28 Nos of 300 meter Tall buildings, 102 Nos of 200 meter buildings and 207 Nos of 150 meter buildings exist in UAE. Majority of these building are constructed in the states of Abu Dhabi and Dubai. The Study reveals that majority of the facade of these tall building are metal curtain wall with aluminum and glass. Further study on the criterion and the governing criteria in the selection of facades and the need and possibility of an integrated decision making process in the selection of façade is recommended.

Key Words: - Tall Buildings, United Arab Emirates, Facades

1.1 Introduction

United Arab Emirates is a nation situated on the Arabian Peninsula, on the northwestern coast of the Gulf of Oman and the south eastern coast of the Persian Gulf. United Arab Emirates comprises of seven 'states' and was established on 2 December 1971 as a federation. Six of the seven States Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Sharjah, Ajman, Umm Al Quwain and Fujairah combined on that date, the seventh state, Ras Al Khaimah, joined the federation on 10 February 1972. The seven emirates were formerly known as the Trucial States, in reference to the treaty relations established with the British in the 19th Century. Artifacts discovered in the UAE show an extensive history of human inhabitation and regional trade including with Mesopotamia. As of today, United Arab Emirates is a highly developed, most modern country with a greatly diversified economy, with Dubai in particular developing into a global hub for real estate, tourism, retail, and finance, home to the world's tallest building, largest man-made seaport and busiest international airport. The Aim of this research study is to understand the type of facades of the tall buildings in UAE. In order to achieve the aims and objectives of this study, it is important to determine the most appropriate methodology for this study. Scandura & Williams (2000)^[1] noted that the impact of management studies often depends "upon the appropriateness of the research methods chosen". This further highlights the prominence that the researcher needs to select the right approach if the end-result is expected to be valuable and meaningful from a management perspective.

1.2 Rationale of the Study

With the increasing intricacies in facade materials, aesthetic, performance, regulatory compliance requirements, specification and technology, the facade project management becomes profound and compound. There are tasks to make cognizant decisions by the proper parties at the right levels for the right selection of facades and its execution.

Hence this research study will provide basic information's for further studies to identify the impacts of decisions in façade project management and to explore the feasibility of integrated decision making process in the project management of facades for the tall building of UAE.

History of Babel Tower shows that Middle East is the region where tall buildings initiated. Tallest building in the Middle East, Baynunah Tower, and Abu Dhabi has been constructed in 1993 and the tallest building in the world, Burj Khalifa in Dubai has been constructed and inaugurated in the year of 2009. Since then, many other iconic tall building has been constructed in UAE like Marina 101 in Dubai. During this period of construction it has been observed that decisions in the project management of facades has a great impact in the tall building construction particularly related to its performance, cost, aesthetics, timely completion etc.? Decision making process requires technical knowledge, appropriate strategies for management and the interchange of information. Proper selection of facades and façade specialist contractor at early stage will avoid project delays, cost variations or any type of compromises which cause poor performance of façade system.

Since planning and control is the success of any project management, integrated decisions at the early stage is important to avoid any later deviations and subsequent time or cost overrun. Integrated decision making process is also a key factor to successful facade project management especially for the tall buildings.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this research study in the order of importance are as follows:

1. To study chronology of Tall buildings Constructed in United Arab Emirates.
2. To explore the type of facades carefully chosen for the construction of these all buildings.

1.4 Review of Literature

Literature review helps to have a better understanding on facades particularly about facade project management related to tall buildings, recent research on selection of facades especially related to tall buildings, construction management concepts and initiatives, communication and knowledge management in construction and Integrated decision making Process and its feasibility

Authors, Trevor c. Pavitt & Alister G. F. Gibb ^[2], explains in their paper “Managing Cladding Interfaces with in the building facade: Decision Making and Timing” that the key area for the improvement for construction process lies in managing the interfaces between building facade and critical building elements.

Authors, Qiang Du, Rui Yang and Stephen Ledbetter ^[3] explains in “The information sources in building cladding supply chain” The increasing complexity of the cladding procurement and fragmentation of the supply chain bring challenges for information management.

Authors, Helen Garmstonl, Wei Pan and Pieter de Wilde^[4] of Plymouth University, Drake Circus, Plymouth, PL4 8AA, UK briefs in “Decision-making in facade selection for multi-storey buildings” that in current building practice, facade selection appears to be largely driven by cost considerations and building aesthetics. However, given the many demands on buildings, this approach can expose the real estate businesses and building inhabitants to risk. Authors did not attempt to explain the types of facades and its performance requirement rather talks about the share of curtain wall in a building cost wise and the need of sustainable designs and the ingredients of design are briefed. Multi-storey buildings "are required to meet certain statutory drivers, such as building regulations, of which many also apply to single-storey buildings. However, due to the potential height of multi-storey buildings; these statutory drivers often contain stricter elements solely for use on multi-storey buildings.

Akbar R Tamboli ^[5] clarify Tall and Supertall buildings - Planning and Design is a book that assembles and explains the planning, design and construction of tall and super tall buildings. It is intended to help architects, engineers and students of civil engineering/ mechanical engineering and architecture with an authoritative reference work on tall and super tall buildings.

Alan J Brooks ^[6], in his book “Cladding of Buildings” gives a very detailed information regarding the types of claddings of a building including Precast Concrete Cladding, Glass Reinforced Polyester, Glass Fibre Reinforced Cement, Formed metal Including Profiled Metal, Sheet Metal Composite metal Panels and Rain Screen, Curtain walling - Glazing Systems. This book has first published in 1983, since then there have been considerable developments in cladding systems and their use in architectural projects. Based on above facts "a study on facades of Tall buildings in UAE" is more relevant.

1.5 Research Gap

Research gap” is defined as an area of research that is significantly immature and/or is suffering from a significant lack of available information and knowledge in the field. **William Baker, Skidmore, Owings & Merrill** said, “Each discipline involved in tall buildings is continually evolving its ‘science,’ but also has immediate problems to solve on current projects. One cannot wait to build until we know all there is to know. Conversely, just because we are currently creating buildings, we cannot forget that we must broaden our knowledge and extend the science of tall buildings.”

It is broadly acknowledged that we are now experiencing a huge swell in tall building construction internationally, with more and taller skyscrapers being designed, constructed and completed since 2000 than at any other time in history. The statistics demonstrating this are overwhelming. According to the CTBUH tall building database, it has been shown, for example, that 265 buildings measuring 200 meters or taller were completed around the world prior to the year 2000. However, in the 12 years that followed, to the end of 2016, almost double this number has been built, with 518 skyscrapers completed. Although Asia, and in particular China, dominate tall building construction globally, what is fascinating is that this growth is not limited to any one geographic region. There are 543 cities around the world which embrace at least one building taller than 100 meters as a significant element within their urban realm.

The development of any tall building loads a significant level of investment – not only monetarily, but also in terms of consultant expertise and time. Due to this, built high-rises are increasingly being used as test beds for innovative new ideas, technologies and systems. It is clear, then, that tall building research is important and can play a significant role in the development of the cities of the future. Published literature provides the progress of related research and background for further research. The limited and insufficient academic literature regarding decision making process in the project management of facades for tall building in UAE further emphasize the need for the research to fill the gap.

It is also noteworthy to high light that the limited and insufficient literature in the field motivated Council on Tall buildings and Urban Habitat (CTBUH) to publish a “Road Map on the Future needs of Tall Buildings” with the editors Philip Old Field, Dario Trabuccu and Antony Wood. William Baker the trustee of CTBUH encouraged all in his speech on September 2013 that there is a need for research in all aspects of tall buildings. These needs span numerous categories, including occupant comfort and experience, sustainable materials, urban infrastructure, energy and carbon issues, office, and residential systems, structural systems, transportation, life safety, security, evacuation procedures, and so on. Unfortunately, for such a large industry, there is remarkably little formal research.

1.6 Research Methods

Data collection methods may be divided into the primary data collection and the secondary data collection. The secondary data is the form of data sets that have been previously collected, and it is observed that "data quality is always a concern". Regarding building statistics secondary data Published by the Council on Tall Buildings and Urban Habitat (CTBUH) has been used. Cluster analysis has been followed for the identification of tall buildings in UAE and primary data has been collected through site survey regarding the type of facades employed for the buildings.

1.7 Chronology of Tall Buildings in UAE.

Table 1.1 shows the chronology of the tall building in UAE. From 1799 till 1973 Al Fahdi fort was the tallest building UAE and in fact it was a single story building. From 1973 till 1978 Sheikh Rashid Building became the tallest building in UAE. Construction of World trade center is finished in 1979 and which stayed as the tallest building till 1994. Baynunah Tower in Abu Dhabi has been constructed in 1994 and the building became the tallest building in Middle East and the tallest in UAE till 1999. Burj Al Arab has been constructed and inaugurated in the year of 1999 and till 2000 this was the tallest building in UAE. In the year of 2000 Emirates twin tower has been constructed and which has been labelled as the tallest building in UAE till 2009. Al Mas Tower has been finished and it gained a short period till 2010 as the tallest building in UAE. In 2010 UAE, s Tallest building Burj Khalifa, which stands 828 mm high has been inaugurated and which became the tallest building in the world. A Close observation on facades of these buildings reveals that the facades of first two buildings were constructed in using block work masonry and concrete and for the world trade center precast concrete and punch windows were used as facades. From Bainunah tower onwards the facades of Tall building were changed to Unitized aluminium and glazed curtain wall and Aluminium composite panel cladding.

TABLE 1.1 CHRONOLOGY OF TALL BUILDINGS IN UAE

SL NO	BUILDING	YEAR	HEIGHT METERS	NUMBER OF FLOORS	STATE	FAÇADE TYPE	IMAGE
1	AL FAHDI FORT	1799–1973	23	1	DUBAI	MASONRY	
2	SHEIKH RASHID BUILDING	1973-1978		15	DUBAI	CONCRETE	
3	DUBAI WORLD TRADE CENTER	1979–1994	149	39	DUBAI	PRECAST AND PUNCH WINDOWS	
4	BAYNUNAH HILTON TOWER HOTEL	1994–1999	165	42	ABU DHABI	GLAZED METAL CURTAIN WALL	
5	BURJ AL ARAB	1999–2000	321	60	DUBAI	GLAZED METAL CURTAIN WALL & CLADDING	

6	EMIRATES OFFICE TOWER	2000–2009	355	54	DUBAI	GLAZED CURTAIN WALL	
7	ALMAS TOWER	2009–2010	360	74	DUBAI	GLAZED CURTAIN WALL & CLADDING	
8	BURJ KHALIFA	2010–PRESENT	828	160	DUBAI	GLAZED CURTAIN WALL	

Source: - <https://en.wikipedia.org>

1.8 Tall Buildings in United Arab Emirates.

There is no absolute agreed definition of what constitutes a “Tall building”. The CTBUH defines “Supertall” as building over 300 meters in height and a “Mega tall” as a building over 600 meters in height. In United Arab Emirates, there are 336 completed high-rises, 28 of which stand taller than 300 meters, 102 of which stand taller than 200 meters and 207 of which stand taller than 150 meter. Table 1.2 and Fig. 1.1 shows the Statistics of Tall buildings in UAE comparing to the Tall buildings of world.

TABLE 1.2. TALL BUILDINGS COMPARISON – UAE & AROUND WORLD

HEIGHT	ABOVE 300 METER	ABOVE 200 METER	ABOVE 150 METER
AROUND THE WORLD	106	1061	3570
UNITED ARAB EMIRATES	28	102	207
PERCENTAGE	25.5%	9.6%	5.8%

Source : The Global building database of the CTBUH

FIG 1.1 TALL BUILDING COMPARISON – UAE & AROUND THE WORLD

According to the tall building database of CTBUH, Dubai has 24 completed buildings that rise at least 300 meters in height, which is more than any other city in the world. While Dubai has 102 completed buildings that rise at least 200 meters in height, again which is more than any other city in the world. Based on the average height of the ten tallest completed buildings, Dubai has the tallest skyline in the Middle East and as of 2016 the skyline of Dubai is ranked sixth in the world with 270 buildings rising at least 150 meters in height. As of 2016, 363 new tall buildings are under construction in Dubai; additionally, there are over 640 active high-rise developments that have been proposed for construction in the city. Table 1.3 and Fig. 1.2 shows the Statistics of Tall buildings in different states of UAE.

TABLE 1.3. NUMBER OF TALL BUILDINGS IN THE STATES OF UAE

HEIGHT	ABOVE 300 METER	ABOVE 200 METER	ABOVE 150 METER	TOTAL BUILDING
ABUDHABI	4	21	31	56
ALAIN	0	0	0	0
DUBAI	24	78	169	270
SHARJAH	0	2	8	10
AJMAN	0	1	1	2
FUJAIRAH	0	0	2	2
RAS AL KHAIMAH	0	0	3	3

Source : The Global building database of the CTBUH

FIG 1.2 NUMBER OF TALL BUILDINGS IN THE STATES OF UAE

1.9 Facades of Tall Building in UAE – Above 300 Meters

Aim of this study is to identify the type of façades employed in Super Tall buildings (Above 300m). Following 28 buildings identified as super tall buildings in the land of UAE. (CTBUH 2016). Out of these 28 Super Tall buildings 4 is situated in Abu Dhabi and 24 exists in Dubai. Below Table show the height of the buildings and its facades. A site survey has been conducted to identify the type facades used for the external envelope of these 28 buildings.

TABLE 1.4. SUPER TALL BUILDINGS IN UAE

SL NOS	BUILDING	YEAR	HEIGHT METERS	NUMBER OF FLOORS	STATE	FAÇADE TYPE	IMAGE
1	Burj Khalifa	2010	828	163	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall	
2	Marina 101	2016	426.5	101	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
3	Prices Tower	2012	413.4	101	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	

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SL NOS	BUILDING	YEAR	HEIGHT METERS	NUMBER OF FLOORS	STATE	FAÇADE TYPE	IMAGE
4	23 Marina	2012	392.4	88	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
5	Burj Mohammed Bin Rashid	2014	381.2	88	Abu Dhabi	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
6	Elite Residence	2012	380.5	87	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
7	The Address the BLVD	2016	368	72	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
8	Al Mas Tower	2008	360	68	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
9	JW Marriott Marquis Hotel Tower 1	2012	355.4	82	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
10	JW Marriott Marquis Hotel Tower 2	2013	355.4	82	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
11	Emirates Tower 1	2000	354.6	54	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
12	The Torch	2011	352	86	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
13	Ahmed Abdul Rahim Al Attar Tower	2017	342	76	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	

SL NOS	BUILDING	YEAR	HEIGHT METERS	NUMBER OF FLOORS	STATE	FAÇADE TYPE	IMAGE
14	Adnoc Head Quarters	2015	342	65	Abu Dhabi	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
15	Damac Heights	2017	335.3	88	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
16	Rose Rayhaan by Rotana	2007	333	71	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
17	Al Yaqoub Tower	2013	328	69	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
18	The Index	2010	326	80	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
19	The Land Mark	2013	324	72	Abu Dhabi	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
20	Burj Al Arab	1999	321	56	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
21	HHHR Tower	2010	317.6	72	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
22	Ocean Heights	2010	310	83	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
23	Emirates Tower Two	2000	309	56	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	

SL NOS	BUILDING	YEAR	HEIGHT METERS	NUMBER OF FLOORS	STATE	FACADE TYPE	IMAGE
24	Cayan Tower	2013	306.4	73	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
25	Etihad Towers T2	2008	305	80	Abu Dhabi	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
26	The Address	2008	302.2	63	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
27	Al Habtoor City Tower 1	2017	300	74	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	
28	Al Habtoor City Tower 2	2017	300	74	Dubai	Glazed Curtain Wall & Cladding	

Source: The Global building database of the CTBUH & Site Survey

1.10 Conclusions

This study provided a clear understanding about the façades of Super Tall buildings in UAE. The main finding gained through this study is that majority of the façades of Super Tall buildings are Aluminum and glazed curtain wall especially Unitized Curtain wall type of Construction which is identified through site survey. This information can be used for further study on project management of the façades of Tall buildings in UAE.

1.11 Recommendation for future Works

According to the results, many efforts need to be made in future work, including the following:-

- Investigate decision making process in the selection facades for the Tall Buildings in UAE
- Critical study on Criteria Controls the decisions of Selection of Facades for Tall Building
- To Explore governing Criteria in the selection Facades for Tall Buildings
- Investigate feasibility for integrated decision making process in the selection of Facades.

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